

Knowledge Management and Lifelong Learning in the Workplace

The Impact of Savoir Transfer on Continuous Work-based Learning in HEIs – Case of Moroccan Universities

Gestion des Connaissances et Formation tout au Long de la Vie au Travail

L'impact du Transfert des Savoirs sur l'Apprentissage Continu en Situation de Travail dans les EES – Cas des Universités Marocaines.

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Abstract

In an era where knowledge is a “currency” and an indicator of performance, it has become important to make it last. For it to be constant, it has to be conserved at an organizational level, which implies engaging institutional mechanisms. Knowledge Management (KM) allows to store and apply valuable knowledge and skills, transfer it to individuals and groups and allows to create an informal work-based learning space. Learning becomes then continuous, despite age, education or status and throughout the life span. This paper aims to theoretically frame the link between knowledge management and informal lifelong learning (LLL) in the workplace, precisely in the context of knowledge economies. The empirical research focuses on the case of Moroccan Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to verify if they align with KM enablers and examine if they would provide a favorable environment for knowledge transfer and, by extension, for lifelong learning. To accomplish these objectives, the first part is dedicated to defining the basic concepts of the discussion and displaying their characteristics/correlations based on literature. The second part clearly indicates our positioning towards the matter and explains the steps of the survey’s elaborations, whilst the last part discusses responses and their interpretations. The paper concludes with the research limitations and a few proposals to improve the Moroccan participation in KM and LLL.

Keywords: Knowledge Economy – Knowledge Management – Morocco – Higher Education Institutions – Education - Work-based Learning – Informal Learning - Lifelong Learning

Introduction

As knowledge-based economies continue to grow, an organization's employees' skills are considered more as a valuable resource, asset, for its success. The intellectual and cognitive capital makes organizational performance more effective. Therefore, knowledge transfer allows the organizations to generate the expertise that remains tacit and transmit it, in order to facilitate problem-solving and the integration of new recruits. Therefore, acquiring knowledge becomes a daily activity and a continuous process that guarantees a lifelong learning dynamic, which is a systemic response to knowledge instability.

In this context, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), being associated with learning and knowledge production should be first to valorize and capitalize on the expertise of its collaborators. However, only few universities seem to be preserving and disseminating their "savoir", especially in Morocco.

Furthermore, studies have shown that the majority of organizations know that knowledge exists but identifying it and using it is problematic (Alavi and E. Leidner, 2001). Other authors have found that organizations face difficulties to leverage knowledge even if they are aware of its importance for their development.

On the other hand, the collaborators' knowledge in the academic context has not been sufficiently preserved nor transferred, as mentioned before. More specifically, literature suggests that the Moroccan university does not manage or retain knowledge. These limits have caused the university to lose on terms of international and national competitiveness and efficiency.

Therefore, our research will aim to (i) understand, through the literature, how knowledge production is influenced by the context of Knowledge Economy; (ii) explore the relation/correlation between knowledge management and lifelong learning; (iii) provide empirical data on knowledge management in Moroccan HEIs; and (iv) study the possible implications of knowledge management for skill development in the workplace.

To do so, our article will first, start by setting the context in which main concepts like knowledge and Knowledge Economy are defined. Next, we discuss the importance of Knowledge Management as an institutional mechanism for preserving the cognitive capital of organizations. Lastly, the theoretical framework closes on the definition of lifelong learning in

the workplace, which we consider as a systemic response to the knowledge instability problematic.

Empirically, the article focuses mainly on an assessment of Knowledge Management enablers in the Moroccan academic context. The objective of the conducted survey is to determine whether HEIs in Morocco would be a favorable environment to apply and optimize KM processes, which, by extension, would allow us to connect these processes to a lifelong learning prospective aiming to improve higher education.

1. Theoretical Framework

1.1. Knowledge: a “currency” in the context of knowledge economies

1.1.1. Knowledge

According to Dretske (1981),” *knowledge is identified with information-produced (or sustained) belief, but the information a person receives is relative to what he or she already knows about the possibilities at the source*” (ibid. p. 86). To Alavi and Leidner (2001), knowledge is” *information held in the minds of individuals: It is personalized information (which may or may not be new, unique, useful or specific), related to facts, procedures, concepts, interpretations, ideas, observations and judgments*” (p109). Nakra (2000) defines knowledge as “*relevant information contained in documents, communication tools, processes, and people’s minds, required for decision-making or to support work processes*”.

Therefore, knowledge is personalized information that is held in documents and/or people’s minds, which facilitates the process of decision-making based on ideas, observations, judgments... it is relevant information that depends on how the knowledge provider conceives that knowledge.

Knowledge became one of the major levers of economic, political and cultural development (UNESCO,2005). The importance of knowledge lies in its ability to determine and transform the capabilities of humanity. With the emergence of “knowledge societies”, the production of knowledge, its processing as well as its impact on human rights and values became an indicator to measure a population’s performance in terms of growth and sustainable development (UNESCO, 2005; IIEP, 2007).

1.1.2. Explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge

Researchers distinguish between explicit and tacit knowledge. This distinction was first introduced by Michael Polanyi in 1967, and then developed by Nonaka and Takeuchi in 1997.

“Explicit Knowledge” was referred to as a “*form of knowledge that can be transmitted without loss through speech, once the syntax rules of the language are known and concepts representative of the semantics of this language. A standardized code, explicit, shared, allows to convey the information carrying this knowledge*” (Reix, 1995).

Thus, explicit knowledge is a codified and structured knowledge, easily communicable and transmissible. It can be shared in its entirety, in written or oral form.

Reix (1995) also defined tacit knowledge. He considered it as “*a form of knowledge that’s impossible (or difficult) to translate in a speech*” (Reix, 1995).

So, tacit knowledge is a type of knowledge that people use without needing to talk about it, usually because it is something they are familiar with. It can be personal knowledge, like knowing how to do something without needing to tell anyone, or it can be knowledge that is embedded in a person's brain, like the way people use mental models to figure out how things work.

1.1.3. Knowledge Economy

A society that is centered on knowledge represents a framework where investing in education and training becomes a necessity. According to a publication of the World Bank Group, one of the main pillars of a Knowledge Economy (KE) is “educated and skilled workers” who adapt their competencies and upgrade their skills continuously (Derek et al., 2006).

A KE presents many advantages for development. However, other studies argue that the shift to Knowledge Economies resulted in a “gap”, considering the unexpected acceleration of knowledge production (David and Foray, 2002). This “gap” that resides between tangible and intangible capitals simply represents the delay of what we actually “do” in reference to what we “know”.

1.1.4. Knowledge production

University is an organization where work is intellectual and where the majority of the workforce is made up of qualified employees (Alvesson, 2000). The university, through its various roles based on the creation, codification and dissemination of knowledge, perfectly meets this definition. Researchers agree that the university is the organization with the greatest potential for creating knowledge (Ramachandran et al., 2013).

Authors assigned different roles to the university. Thus, they distinguish three major roles: *teaching, research* and *support activities* such as consulting, lifelong learning or cooperation. Other authors have detailed these roles between initial and continuing training, the scientific research, international cooperation and finally guidance and integration (Ramachandran et al., 2013). However, recent studies argued that universities do not hold up to these roles any longer.

As the production and creation of knowledge is not monopolized by universities, they are considered as a component of a global network and operate according to “socially distributed” system driven by economic growth and markets (Le Grange, 2012).

So, as we continue to grow in this new context where economic development is based on knowledge production, the strategic value of “savoir” increases continuously (Suciu et al., 2010). The need to protect one the most important assets for growth is becoming a priority, especially in higher education institutions (HEIs). However, this process of preserving knowledge in any organization must be based on specific guidelines and institutional, well-structured mechanisms to ensure efficacy and quality.

1.2. What is conserved is forever maintained: Knowledge transfer tools

1.2.1. Knowledge management

Von Krogh (1998) suggests that knowledge management (KM) “refers to *identifying and leveraging the collective knowledge to help the organization compete*”. Alavi et Leidner (1999) suggest that knowledge management is “*a systemically and organizationally specified process for acquiring, organize, communicate both the tacit and explicit knowledge of so that other employees can use them to be efficient and productive in their work*”.

Thus, knowledge management is defined as a systematic and organizational process that allows organizations to not only generate and share tacit and explicit knowledge with employees, but to manage it to increase efficiency and productivity.

Knowledge management is not a new practice (Hansen et al, 1999). Indeed, for several centuries the know-how has been passed down from generation to generation, from a master to his apprentice. Nevertheless, it was at the dawn of the 1990s that interest in this practice has been shown within organizations.

In this context, authors studied four main KM enablers that should be established within an organization or a HEI in our case, in order to win in terms of KM practices. Arthur Andersen and the American Productivity and Quality Centre (APQC) have implemented a model of organizational knowledge management which explained that KM is supported by leadership, organizational culture, Information Technologies (IT) and performance measurement.

The KM processes necessary for an organization to be successful include activities like creating knowledge, storing information, sharing information, and using that knowledge to improve

performance. The same classification was used later by Mertins et al. (2003) who defined KM as the process through which organizations apply, distribute, generate and store knowledge.

1.2.2. Knowledge transfer

The objective of knowledge sharing is to share the correct form of knowledge with the correct people at the correct time. Many technological tools have been developed to facilitate knowledge transfer; some of them are the email, discussion forums, videoconferencing, intranet systems and the internet. These tools that share knowledge can be formal and informal, personal or impersonal (Alavi and Leidner, 2001).

According to research done by Teng et Hawamdeh (2002), Jundale et Navale (2009), Nilsook et Sriwongkol (2009) and Songsangyos (2012), knowledge transfer in universities has a huge added value that allows the organizations to develop and thrive within the socio-economic environment.

To illustrate, among some of the advantages mentioned by the researchers above, we can cite: *improving the quality and efficiency of teaching, improving competitiveness vis-à-vis national and international competition, retaining important intellectual assets after staff leave the organization, developing a “knowledge base” or organizational memory, identifying experts by field and share and exchange experiences on successful projects or others that have failed (apprenticeship from errors), improving organizational learning and innovation capacity, saving time and effort by reducing redundant work and avoiding “reinventing the wheel”, developing human resources, improving communication at the level of staff and top management, finally, promoting a culture of sharing within the organization, etc.*

Knowledge transfer depends on a lot of factors so it can be successfully implemented within organizations. For instance, the characteristics of the sender, those of the receiver and the context of transfer can have a huge impact on the process (Zahir and Rabeh-rabbou, 2021).

1.2.3. Knowledge transfer process

Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) developed a knowledge creation model in which they describe and analyze the conditions that lead to generating knowledge within organizations. Their model is based on four main interactions that occur between tacit and explicit knowledges. The SECI model stands for socialization, exteriorization, combination and internalization (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1997):

Figure N°1: The SECI model

Source: Nonaka and Takeuchi (1997)

- (S) **Socialization**: conversion from tacit knowledge to tacit knowledge
- (E) **Exteriorization**: conversion of tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge
- (C) **Combination**: conversion from explicit knowledge to explicit knowledge
- (I) **Internalization**: conversion from explicit knowledge to tacit knowledge

The model is based on the assumption that the knowledge is a dynamic construct that is created at the end of the interaction between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge (Boukhari and Limamy, 2016). Thus, according to Nonaka and Takeuchi, these knowledge conversion processes allow knowledge to evolve from an individual level to an organizational one. Furthermore, Nonaka and Konna (1998) studied the conditions that are optimal for knowledge creation within an organization. They suggested a concept called “*ba*” which determines the mutual context of those who take action and interact in the process of knowledge transfer.

1.2.4. Knowledge transfer tools

The aim of the following table is to group means of communication that facilitate the sharing and creation of knowledge. These tools could be summarized as follows:

Tableau N°1: Knowledge transfer tools adjusted to Nonaka and Takeuchi’s SECI model

		TO	
		Tacit	Explicit
FROM	Tacit	Socialization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert localization - Expertise exchange 	Externalization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Groupware tools - E-learning tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electronic messaging • Mailing- lists • Discussion forums • Chat
	Explicit	Internationalization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Text mining - knowledge mapping - visualization tools - E-learning tools 	Combination Electronic Document Management
			Acquisition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Text mining - Data mining
			Organization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data warehouse - Thesaurus - Semantic networks - Expert systems - Case-based reasoning systems - Bayesian networks
Access <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indexing and search engine - Agents 			
		Transfer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Groupware tools - Workflow tools - Push tools 	

Source: Authors

We have seen in this section that the establishment of a knowledge management approach requires two key dimensions: methods and technologies for the dissemination and sharing of this knowledge.

However, knowledge management and transfer are not only a technical way of storing knowledge. They provide the organizations, notably universities, with the possibility of establishing a “learning culture” (Suciu et al., 2010), which then promotes initiative. In simple words, KM fosters continuous sustained learning throughout life, despite age groups, educational backgrounds or learning modes (formal, non-formal, informal).

1.3. Knowledge instability? - Lifelong learning is the answer

1.3.1. Lifelong Learning

The concept of “Lifelong Learning” (LLL) describes the process of constant and continuous learning that occurs both within and beyond formal educational structures, throughout one’s lifetime. This means that an individual could acquire knowledge in an institution, but also in events, workshops, with friends or colleagues, in informal settings, etc. It must simply be voluntary, self-motivated and should encompass five elements, notably (i)all age groups, (ii)all levels of education, (iii)all learning modalities, (iv)all spaces and (v)a variety of purposes (UIL, 2022). LLL evolved into a governance tool and became, by the 1990s, an instrument for the modernization of education/training systems (Field, 2001).

Given the place it holds in international discourses, lifelong learning then became an important component in socio-economic growth (UNESCO, 2015). However, it also supports individual development, addresses societal issues and fosters awareness, sustainability as well as resilience (UNESCO, 1976). Literature also shows that LLL aimed to make a collective transformation through human rights and social justice (Barros, 2012). According to the Faure Report (1972), lifelong learning is a pathway to democracy, that encourages cooperation and supports societal well-being.

1.3.2. Informal learning

As the triadic classification dictates, education and learning occur in three settings: (i)formal, (ii)non-formal and (iii)informal. In the present paper, we will consider informal learning, as it represents daily knowledge acquiring processes and does not lead to any recognized qualifications. Yet, to define informal learning, it would be useful to contrast it to formal learning (Holmgren and Sjöberg, 2022). According to the literature, formal learning is defined as “being undertaken intentionally to develop specific knowledge and competences” (Kyndt et al., 2016; Eraut, 2004). It is often described as structured, planned, goal-oriented learning process (Marsick and Watkins, 2001).

In this context, informal workplace learning is more accurate. In the workplace, collaborators learning from each other through support, observing or sharing, which creates a dynamic between work and learning (OECD, 2025).

Furthermore, even though informal learning is essential for individual development as well as organizational performance (OECD,2025), it remains challenging to conceptualize and measure because it is context- related. This also explains why research about workplace learning has increased and it is becoming an extensive field that focuses on individual, collective and organizational learning (Lecat et al., 2018; Tynjälä, 2008).

1.3.3. Work-based learning

As the name indicates, work-based learning (WBL) refers to the various ways in which an individual or employee acquires knowledge in a real work environment. According to the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training, WBL improves employability, which optimizes professional development and facilitates access to jobs (CEDEFOP, 2017). On the other hand, different studies have also demonstrated obstacles related to WBL. In fact, work-based knowledge is context-related, which makes public policy support challenging. Policy-makers find it difficult to choose what form of WBL to support or how. In addition to that, there is the risk of poaching, the challenge of knowledge recognition and the lack of legal structure (ETF, 2013).

Another aspect of WBL to focus on is the quality of learning, despite its benefits. Authors stressed that the learning environment of WBL is important (Nijhof and Nieuwenhuis, 2008). The conditions in which WBL occurs should be “designed for learning”, effective and efficient, providing learners with motivation and support (ETF, 2013).

1.4. KM in HEIs around the world: real-life examples

There are a lot of new people coming into the education sector, who are interested in using corporate knowledge management systems. Knowledge management is the task of developing and using an organization's physical and intangible knowledge resources. Tangible assets include the results of research and development (R&D) teams, information about customers, suppliers, products, and competitors. Intangible assets include the skills and knowledge of employees. KM refers to the totality of organizational strategies aimed at creating an intelligent organization, which is able to learn from past experiences, and use its physical and intangible assets to create new knowledge. At the individual level, KM focuses on the skills and capabilities of employees.

Many researchers worked on suggesting tools and mechanisms that allow implementing KM practices within universities. Richards-Kennedy and Brice (2018) suggested that knowledge

brokerage is an important role that regional universities play to help Caribbean states meet the 2030 development agenda. As Caribbean universities continue to evolve, it is important that public engagement and linkage and exchange mechanisms are strengthened so that universities can carry out their developmental and entrepreneurial missions. The article discusses how the societal impact of research can be strengthened by knowledge brokerage activities. It points out useful strategies for reducing the knowledge to policy/practice gap in the Caribbean. The article looks at the field of knowledge brokerage, which is the process of transferring knowledge from one person or group to another. It studies how this is done, and how it can help to improve the effectiveness of research and development (R&D) projects. According to Ahmadi & Ahmadi (2012), the Iranian University is developing in a very difficult context marked by increasing competitiveness. To cope with this, the implementation of a KM approach is necessary. This will, among other things, create and develop knowledge bases and improve access, dissemination and exploitation of the knowledge created. This paper argues that knowledge management practices and tools can help universities meet the demands of today's global marketplace. Universities can benefit from KM by creating and managing relevant knowledge repositories, improving access to knowledge, enhancing the knowledge environment, and valuing knowledge. Ramachandran et al. (2013) explained that the KM approach and its various strategic levers, at knowledge: culture, information technology, the leadership and performance indicators, are used of the four Malaysian universities studied. However, the level of enforcement is at an average level. It is therefore need to raise the awareness of teachers about the importance of KM and the use of management systems knowledge. Trivella and Dimitrios (2015) think that it is essential to define a KM strategy within the Greek public universities. This strategy, derived from companies and large groups, is based, among other things, on information and communication, whose role is to disseminate knowledge. This strategy would allow universities European Parliament and the European Parliament competitive at national and European level. They suggested that simulation models can be used to help manage knowledge and help universities stay ahead of the competition. They can be a great resource for future success in public universities.

Desireé Joy Cranfield and John Taylor from University of Southampton, United Kingdom have published an article of a case study conducted at seven Higher Education Institutions. The article came out under the title “Knowledge Management and Higher Education: A UK Case Study”. The study looked at different universities in the UK and found some interesting things about how they use knowledge management (KM) as a tool for managing their work. Some

universities are starting to prioritize KM, but it can be difficult to get everyone on board because academics have their own way of doing things. It's important for universities to understand the benefits of KM and how it can help them do their work better. Some people don't like the word "manage" because it sounds too business-like, so universities need to find a way to talk about KM that everyone can agree on and hence the role of the vice-principal: the knowledge manager is that of facilitator and enabler of various activities that would count as KM. The higher education context would benefit greatly from a taxonomy that specifically adapts to its context. The management structure of a university affects its ability to react quickly to external influences and constraints: the universities have become more and more decentralized, budgets and thus power has been shifted to the school or university management. The consequence is that colleges/faculties, and thereby the leaders or deans, become omnipotent, which tends to prevent the "center" from making systemic or institution-wide changes without the express approval and supporting funding of the deans/leaders. The positive side of this structure is that when there are an environment and culture of collaboration and trust, the center must obtain approval from all deans before it can make systemic changes that improve the success of the initiative. Centralized models do not have this problem and it has been found that the newer, modern universities tend to be more entrepreneurial and adopt the more centralized model. There is a connection between the history of the institution and its ability to respond to the challenges of the 21st century knowledge economy: the universities that were undergoing a major transformation, those that changed their status from polytechnic to university in 1992, expressed the need for an evidence-based benefits of KM or for clear direction from government or funding councils to implement KM. In their opinion, this would tip the scales in favor of KM as the major change they have had to go through in recent years requires a period of stability before further significant changes are implemented. In contrast, the pre-1992 universities are now beginning to fundamentally change their structure, processes and systems and are able to introduce 21st century management tools to ensure they remain at the forefront. In summary, this research has enabled some rich themes and insights regarding the current perception of KM in the higher education context and the factors that hinder or promote its implementation. This paper is talking about two things: what teachers and schools are like, and how that affects how they share information. This research is fascinating in that academic research on KM is becoming increasingly popular and institutions are offering it as an academic program or course, but few have started researching the application or implementation of KM.

2. Methodology

The theoretical framework demonstrated that KM and LLL are related, as they impact and are impacted by organizational performance, notably in HEIs. And after we have positioned universities within the context of knowledge economies, this chapter will present the methodology we adopted to, first, verify the applicability of KM practices in the Moroccan academic framework and examine if these practices will result in enabling lifelong learning. We chose to work on three Moroccan universities as a general case but the focus will be on sub-cases, specific institutions that belong to these universities, to study how the dynamics we explained previously materialize in real life and precisely in Morocco.

Regarding the research paradigm, we choose to adopt a postpositivist worldview. This choice could be justified by the fact that we are starting from a well-defined position and trying to observe the behaviors of employees towards knowledge transfer to study their relation with KM enablers. In the case of our research, we have adopted a deductive approach wherein the reviewed theory would allow us to verify and confirm what we observe empirically.

Thanks to a quantitative study i.e. a survey, we will investigate the answers of the professors of different Moroccan HEIs. The institutions that we have chosen to diffuse our survey are Faculties of juridical, economic and social sciences (FSJES), faculty of educational sciences (FSE) and national schools of commerce and management (ENCG) in Rabat, Kenitra and Casablanca.

2.1. Sample identification: characteristics of the participants

Tableau N°2: Characteristics of the sample

	Characteristics of the sample	Number (T= 35)
Gender	Male	26
	female	9
Age range	25 – 35 years old	3
	35 – 45 years old	9
	45+ years old	23
Profession	HE professor	33
	Associate professor	2
Specialty	History	1
	Management & economy	18
	Math & IT	3
	Biotechnology	2
	Law	5
	Linguistics & com	6

Source: Authors

2.2. Data analysis: Google Sheets

Google Sheets offers a variety of functions, such as:

_Free and Available: Offers basic functionality for free. This allows a wide range of users to access spreadsheet functionality without having to purchase expensive software licenses.

_Advanced calculation and formatting features - Google Sheets offers a comprehensive set of calculation and formatting features. You can use formulas to perform complex calculations, create pivot tables, apply conditional formatting, and customize the appearance of your data. Plus, Google Sheets offers a wide range of pre-built templates to help you get started quickly.

_Integration with other Google tools - Google Sheets integrates seamlessly with other Google tools, such as Google Docs, Google Slides and Google Forms. You can import data from other Google applications, link them together and update them automatically.

2.3. Ethical considerations

The survey was completely anonymous in order to respect the participants' privacy and protect their interests. The questions about demographic information did not require any sort of identification, neither by name nor profession. The selection of participants was done in complete discretion.

3. Findings

In this section, we will interpret the survey's results. For each question, we will represent the number of answers on a graphic so it would be easier to analyze and discuss the results. To analyze the results of our research, we note that they fit into three categories: information about the participants, their behaviors towards knowledge transfer and their work environments. The survey was diffused in French to accommodate participants' needs.

Figure N°2: Age range of participants

Source: Survey's results

Description: The reading of this table reveals that the majority of our participants are 45 years or older. Next come participants ranging from 35 and 45 years old, and last participants who are 25 to 35 years old come last. This shows that 66.7% of the interviewed professors are older than 45.

Figure N°3: Years of experience as a professor

Source: Survey's results

Description: The reading of this figure reveals that the majority of our participants are seniors, which a percentage of means they have 10+ years of experience as professors. Next come participants with 2+ years of experience with a percentage 40% of the interviewed professors.

Figure N°4: Basic understanding of KM

Source: Survey's results

Description: The reading of this graph show that 86.7% of the participants do have a basic understanding of what KM is, whilst 13.3% of those don't.

Figure N°5: Knowledge sharing and/or receiving

Source: Survey's results

Description: The reading of this graph show that the majority of the participants have shared and received knowledge from members of the staff, whilst only 1 participant denied having shared or received any knowledge.

Figure N°6: Top management and sharing behaviors

Source: Survey's results

Description: The reading of the graph showed that the majority of the participants find that the top management contribution is crucial to enable sharing behaviors within the organization. However, 10% of the answers deny that fact and think that knowledge transfer can occur without the intervention of the directory.

Figure N°7: Behavior towards knowledge transfer on platforms

Source: Survey's results

Description: The majority of the participants accept to share their knowledge in both formal and informal situations. However, 16% of them rather share on formal platforms only.

Figure N°8: Motivation to share based on years of experience

Source: Survey's results

Description: The graph shows that the majority of the participants are seniors, which means they have been teaching for 10+ years. We observe that almost 100% of the seniors would be motivated to share knowledge with juniors. This shows that the behavior of human resources towards inter-generational KT impacts its implementation (the more they're motivated, the more knowledge they share).

Another aspect that seems important is measurement performance and how it is impacted by communication with the top management. The following graphic shows how many participants qualifying communication as effective do have performance indicators in the faculty.

Figure N°9: Performance indicators and communication

Source: Survey's results

Description: The participants who qualified the communication with top management as ineffective did not answer “yes” to the question about the presence of common performance indicators. This means that setting an evaluation chart and/or approach that everyone adopts has a positive impact on the quality of communication within universities, as it allows the staff to feel engaged and gives the top management information about its personnel’s performance.

Figure N°10: Communication and sharing behaviors

Source: Survey's results

Description: The graph above shows how effective communication (an aspect of leadership) impact sharing behaviors. In fact, we can see that the numbers of participants that are motivated to share knowledge are the ones who qualified communication effective. Communication, as

mentioned above, is an aspect of leadership. It indicates whether the top management has succeeded in terms of guiding and motivating its staff.

4. Discussion, limitations and perspectives

We can conclude that senior professors in the Moroccan universities are motivated to share their knowledge, since we demonstrated that participants with more years of experience are more motivated (figure 9). This result confirms the importance of the enabler “Human Resources” studied in the previous chapter, in the process of knowledge transfer. From there, we can say that the characteristics of the staff (HR) have a direct influence on the process of knowledge transfer.

The behavior of professors vis-à-vis sharing their knowledge is the most important factor to determine whether the implementation of the platform would be successful or not. However, organizational culture is also fundamental. The values that dominate the work environment control the level of trust that professors hold towards the faculty. If they feel comfortable with the work conditions, they tend to trust the organizations with their intellectual capital.

As shown by the results, the participants who approved of their faculties’ culture made proof of important sharing behaviors. This allows us to conclude that organizational culture, as a KM enabler has a direct impact on knowledge transfer.

Other enablers, such as performance measurement and leadership, can be explained by studying the effectivity of communication within the faculty. Results also proved that the connection between the personnel and the top management can enable knowledge transfer by spreading the right values and engaging the staff in the process of HRM.

Lastly, technology has also been shown to have an impact on knowledge transfer. Our survey’s results proved that a digital tool would facilitate knowledge transfer.

Therefore, we can conclude that the Moroccan university can be an enabling environment for knowledge transfer so it can identify, develop and evaluate their knowledge assets, in order to improve the knowledge sharing process that impacts core activities, like teaching and training... it seems to provide most of the KM enablers discussed in the literature review, which would make it easier to initiate KM in the academic context.

In this context, our results have also shown that knowledge transfer can be a huge asset for the operationalization of juniors. The majority of the participants confirmed the idea that a KM approach would actually help younger employees integrate their work environment easier.

Thus, we found that knowledge transfer is the bridge linking KM enablers to the operationalization of juniors. Since KM enablers facilitate knowledge transfer, and knowledge transfer could help operationalize juniors faster, we can conclude that KM enablers, if available in a work environment, can help integrate new recruits and shorten their learning process.

Even though the empirical study was focused on knowledge management enablers in the Moroccan academic context, the results provide important insight about the learning capacity of HEIs. The availability of KM practices, knowledge transfer, and organizational support result in an environment that facilitates learning beyond the formal settings. Interpreted through the lens of lifelong learning, these results highlight that KM practices work not only as a mechanism to store cognitive resources but also as a foundation that enables sustained, continuous learning. In this perspective, the survey showed the extent to which Moroccan HEIs represent a favorable space to continuous knowledge renewal, a primordial lever of lifelong learning.

Our research, as any other one, has certain inherent limitations that can affect the validity and generalizability of our results. These limitations include the lack of validity of the data due to the limited number of participants, the time constraints and the non-diversity of the specialties of our participants.

First, the lack of data validity is a major concern in our empirical research, especially when our sample of participants is small (35 participants). When we have a small group of participants, it can be difficult to obtain statistically significant results and generalize our findings to a larger population. The results we obtain from this small group may be influenced by specific individual factors and may not accurately represent the reality or diversity of perspectives.

Second, time constraints may also limit the validity and scope of our empirical research. We often face strict deadlines to conduct our studies. In addition, time constraints may limit our ability to adequately track, replicate our study, or deepen certain dimensions of our research, which may compromise the reliability of our findings.

Another major challenge is the non-diversity of the specialties of our participants. When we conduct our empirical research with a small group of participants from a single area of expertise, our results may be biased and not represent in a balanced way different perspectives or

knowledge. For example, our results may be limited to experiences and knowledge specific to that small group, without taking into account other relevant areas or different points of view.

Finally, it should also be stressed that these limits can interact and mutually worsen. For example, the lack of validity of data due to a limited sample may be reinforced by our time constraints, as it may be difficult to expand our sample or conduct a more in-depth study within a specified time frame. Similarly, the non-diversity of our participants' specialties may limit the validity of our data, as it does not reflect the diversity of knowledge and perspectives in our field of research. However, we can suggest a few recommendations that future research may take in consideration to get more accurate results. The empirical study's recommendations highlight several key measures to improve the situation. First, it is essential to have in-depth discussions with relevant stakeholders. These interviews will provide valuable information and diverse perspectives, providing a thorough understanding of the situation and challenges faced by stakeholders. In addition, it is recommended to work on a larger sample to ensure adequate representation of different perspectives and realities. This will result in more robust data and more reliable generalization of results to the target population.

It is also important to conduct experiments in a variety of fields in order to explore the diversity of contexts and gather relevant data for each specific situation. This will help to better understand the factors influencing the results and identify good practices adapted to each context. Universities must also work on their organizational culture to encourage innovation, collaboration and openness to new ideas and technologies. This can foster an environment conducive to continuous improvement and adoption of information and communication technologies (ICT) to facilitate learning and knowledge sharing processes. Another key recommendation is to train teachers on knowledge management (KM) and the effective use of available tools and technologies. This will enable teachers to adopt knowledge-based pedagogical approaches, foster peer-to-peer collaboration and learning, and fully exploit the potential of ICT in transferring their knowledge. Finally, it is advisable to conduct two separate independent studies, one focusing on seniors and the other on juniors. This approach will provide a better understanding of the specific needs, challenges and opportunities of each group of learners, while taking into account generational differences and different ways of learning.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research paper highlights the importance of knowledge management (KM) in the academic context, particularly in Moroccan higher education institutions (HEIs). While universities are renowned for generating knowledge, there is a lack of effective management and preservation of this cognitive capital, especially in Morocco. The study aims to verify the feasibility of implementing KM in the Moroccan academic context. The paper presents a conceptual framework of knowledge economy, KM and LLL, as it explores the literature on KM strategies, mechanisms, and tools, and delves into the transfer of knowledge within organizations and work-based learning. The research also encompasses a quantitative study conducted in various Moroccan universities to analyze professors' behaviors regarding knowledge transfer.

The results proved that KM practices would indeed optimize the learning conditions at the workplace, precisely in HEIs. It was also shown that KM and LLL are tightly related which explains the impact of one on another through knowledge sharing behaviors.

Beyond the Moroccan context, the study could contribute to the current discussions on the role of universities in facing the pressures caused by knowledge economy. It equally underscores that LLL should not only be considered as an educational offering, but as an indicator of institutional stability and resilience, explained through how the knowledge is being managed.

Nevertheless, the study is limited by its focus on KM enablers as indirect factors of learning ability instead of direct indicators of lifelong learning practices. Therefore, future research could extend the study to verify how institutional KM influences learning, innovation and professional development. Fostering KM and lifelong learning remains a promising “strategy” to overall developing both educational policy and academic research.

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